

The Southern Indian Ocean Islands

Introduction

Under the United Nations' Agenda 2030, one indicator of progress towards the conservation of mountain ecosystems (SDG 15.4) is the percentage [%] coverage of important sites for mountain biodiversity (**key biodiversity areas, KBAs**) by **protected areas (PAs)** (SDG 15.4.1). KBAs are areas that significantly contribute to the persistence of global biodiversity. Currently, the indicator is hosted by the UN Environment Programme World Conservation Monitoring Centre (WCMC).

WCMC site-based: The indicator is officially calculated as the **average of the PA coverage of KBAs within a country that are considered mountainous** based on the WCMC mountain definition from 2000¹.

GMBA area-based: As an alternative, the Global Mountain Biodiversity Assessment (GMBA) calculates the indicator as the **ratio between the total area of protected KBAs and the total area of KBAs in mountains**, applying its latest mountain definition from 2022².

Unless mentioned otherwise, the data presented in this one-pager correspond to the GMBA area-based calculation approach, for mountain systems that have KBA (n = 267).

WCMC site-based versus GMBA area-based (temporal comparison)

The Southern Indian Ocean Islands in an international context (2020)

In the left side figure, each point represents one mountain system and its indicator value with both the WCMC site-based and the GMBA area-based calculation approach. The Southern Indian Ocean Islands are marked with the asterisk. Mountain systems close to the diagonal line have a similar indicator value for both calculation approaches, not taking into account the mountain area of a mountain system.

The Southern Indian Ocean Islands, with a GMBA area-based **indicator value of 99.9 for 2020**, have a value lower than 2 other mountain systems. 264 mountain systems have a value lower than the Southern Indian Ocean Islands.

Looking at the spatial disaggregation of the Southern Indian Ocean Islands (overleaf), they span three countries and need a cross-border management.

¹ Kapos et al. (2000) doi:10.1079/9780851994468.0004

² Snethlage et al. (2022) doi:10.1038/s41597-022-01256-y

Mountain range level disaggregation of the GMBA area-based indicator for the Southern Indian Ocean Islands (2020)
Percentage of KBA cover versus percentage of KBA covered by PA

Sub-mountainsystem indicator values

From the six mountain ranges in the Southern Indian Ocean Islands, none are without KBA (pinkish coloring in the country map). From the other six (left side figure), six have an indicator value of at least 95%, with five being fully protected. The latter is 83.3% of those ranges important for mountain biodiversity.

Explore GMBA's global coverage of important sites for mountain biodiversity by protected areas, visit:
gmba.unibe.ch/services/indicators/sdg_1541